

ISic0108

I.Sicily inscription 0108

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]yrim̄ [---][pa]
2. [tr]ono [optimoor]
3. [d]o dec[urion]
4. [u]m pecun[iapub(lica)ob]
5. multa meri[taer]
6. ga rem public[amf(ecit)]
7. ex d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285029

EDR 110885
EDCS 10900637

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0773

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 26

Belvedere, O. 1982. Termini Imerese. Saggi di scavo in Piazza Vittorio Emanuele. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 48: 37-44. At 37

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